

D3.3 Annex 1

Bio4HUMAN KII Guide for Humanitarian SWM Needs Assessment (WP3, T3.3)

Scope: The assessment has the aim of gathering information on the types of waste in DRC and South Sudan, traditional and current methods of SWM, identification of humanitarian supply chains and leaders, and identification of needs of the humanitarian sector in SWM.

Note: This KII guide should be used for discussions separately with individual or homogeneous groups (1-3 participants) of local SWM business representatives. The KII participants are representatives of businesses tackling a) solid waste collection or b) solid waste transformation. All relevant questions in the KII have to be discussed but this doesn't mean that they have to be all posed as such. Information should emerge from the discussion. Additional questions might need to be posed to gather all relevant information.

Key Informant Interviews with local SWM business representatives (individual or homogeneous group, 1-3 participants)

Date:

Location:

Respondent's name(s):

Institution(s):

Respondent's role(s):

Age(s):

Sex(es):

Other information (disability, diversity, etc):

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PIN/PAH staff conducting the interview:

PIN/PAH staff taking notes:

QUESTIONS	Probes (not to be asked all as such but just points to be explored in the conversation if it makes sense, in <i>Italic</i> some references for the discussion)
<p>What type and quantity of waste do you work with? Where do you get it from? (15 min)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What type of solid waste do you work with? Is the waste hazardous or non-hazardous? Can I see it? (<i>observe the quantity and quality, take photos, GPS</i>) 2. How many tuns of waste do you receive / process per month on average? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o If you don't know, why? 3. Where do you get your waste from (rural/urban/camp)? Do these locations change throughout the year? Do you have specific clients who supply you with waste? If yes, who are they? (<i>if possible, ask to see the locations, take photos, GPS</i>) 4. Is the amount of waste available constant throughout the year or are there periods when there is more or less waste available? If yes, when?
<p>What are your solid waste quality standards and do you take measures to protect your waste? (15 min)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the quality standards of waste that you have in order to process the waste? Who/How do you ensure sufficient waste quality for its processing? 2. Do you take any measures to protect your waste from destruction (e.g. weather) or being taken by someone or do you let it be without any supervision? 3. Is the waste storage place an open area or is it a hardened and fenced space? 4. Does the waste storage space have electricity, water, sewage systems, and emission and pollution monitoring systems? 5. If you work with any waste that harms the environment (air, soil, water) or causes health problems, what measures do you take to lower the negative impacts?
<p>What types of SWM services do you provide and what are your SOPs? (15 min)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What type of SWM service do you provide? Do you collect, transport, recycle, compost, re-use waste, or hand it over to some other waste management industry? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o If you transport it to a dump site, where is it? What is its capacity? What type of waste does it collect? Can you show me the dump site? (<i>observe, take photos, GPS</i>) o If you hand the waste to some SWM industry, what is the name of this industry? Can you share a contact? o If you recycle solid waste, do you sort and grade it? What products do you make from solid waste?

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Do you work with sorted waste? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If yes, do you take care of waste sorting or is someone else sorting the waste for you? Who? 3. If you work in solid waste transformation, do you also manage waste collection and transportation? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If not, who manages waste collection and transportation for you and what is their transportation capacity? ○ If yes, what is your collection and transportation capacity? 4. Do you have any SOPs? Can you share with me the hard copy?
<p>Do you work with humanitarian waste or with any humanitarian actors? (5 min)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Do you work with any NGOs or UN agencies either in terms of a) participation in a SWM project or b) managing waste generated by them? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If yes, with who and how do you work with them? ○ Do you know how much waste you manage per month in your cooperation with this humanitarian organization? 2. In your operations, do you distinguish between humanitarian and other waste?
<p>What are the waste management institutions and individuals active in your province/country? How do they function and what are their responsibilities? (10 min)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are other institutions active in the SWM value chain in your province/country (e.g. landfill, recycling or composting businesses, informal recyclers)? Can you give me their contact? 2. What are their roles and responsibilities (collection, transport, storage, recycling, reuse, composting)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Which waste do they manage? ○ How do they function? ○ Are there any fees applied? How does it work? How do they keep records of who pays? ○ How do they protect waste from destruction or rotting or from being taken by others? ○ Are they able to manage all the waste that your province/country produces? ○ If you do not have/use recycling and/or composting services, why? 3. Which of these solid waste management actors do you work with? How?
<p>What are the current practices, requirements and initiatives regarding (humanitarian) solid waste management in your province/country? (15 min)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What is the solid waste management legislation in your country? What are the guidelines for waste storage, protection, and management? Are you able to follow the legislation? If not, why? 2. What are the current practices in your province/country regarding the disposal of humanitarian waste (including packaging, distribution, and construction waste)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Do they differ from practices concerning the disposal of other (“normal”) waste? If yes, how? ○ Do you have any best/worst practices to highlight?

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Does your province/country have any requirements regarding disposal/reuse/repurposing of waste? If yes, what are they? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Is waste being shipped elsewhere for disposal? If so, where? ○ Are there practices particular to a specific type of (humanitarian) packaging waste (e.g. plastic, carton, fabric, wood) or a specific product (e.g. plastic containers, wood pallets, food wrappers, etc.)? 4. Do you have any solid waste management initiatives driven by the government, NGOs, or businesses? If so, what are they?
<p>What are the challenges and opportunities of humanitarian waste management for you and in your province/country? (20 min)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the biggest <u>challenges you are facing</u> in your operations (e.g. <i>inability to pay fees, community behavior, lack of machinery and means of transport</i>)? 2. What are the biggest <u>challenges</u> in terms of solid waste management <u>for your province/country</u> at this moment (e.g. <i>inability to pay fees, community behavior, lack of machinery and means of transport</i>)? If possible, distinguish between waste from NGOs and other waste. 3. How can the current way of handling (humanitarian) waste be improved a) within your business and b) within your province/country? 4. What would you need to improve the current handling of (humanitarian) waste if you are a) business and b) province/country? 5. Are there any local actors/institutions/businesses that could contribute and provide solutions? Are there any actors that are already offering bio-based solutions? 6. Do you know /imagine any ways the bio-products or bio-technologies may improve the waste problems caused by humanitarian interventions? 7. Are there any opportunities for improving solid waste management that a) you are not making use of and b) NGOs/province/country are not making use of? 8. Do you know of any examples of reusing or recycling of solid waste generated by NGOs practiced in your province/country?

D3.3 – Annex 2

Bio4HUMAN KII Guide for Humanitarian SWM Needs Assessment (WP3, T3.3)

Scope: The assessment has the aim of gathering information on the types of waste in DRC and South Sudan, traditional and current methods of SWM, identification of humanitarian supply chains and leaders, and identification of the needs of humanitarian sector in SWM.

Note: This KII guide should be used for discussions separately with individual or homogeneous groups (1-3 participants) of representatives of IDP or refugee camps. The KII participants are representatives of camps that are direct beneficiaries of humanitarian interventions. All relevant questions in the KII have to be discussed but this doesn't mean that they have to be all posed as such. Information should emerge from the discussion. Additional questions might need to be posed to gather all relevant information.

Key Informant Interviews with camp representatives (individual or homogeneous group, 1-3 participants)

Date:

Location:

Respondent's name(s):

Institution(s):

Respondent's role(s):

Type of camp:

Age(s):

Sex(es):

Other information (disability, diversity, etc):

QUESTIONS	Probes (not to be asked all as such but just points to be explored in the conversation if it makes sense, in <i>Italic</i> some references for the discussion)
<p>Which humanitarian organisations are active in your camp and what do they do? (5 min)</p>	<p>5. Which humanitarian organizations have been active in your camp in the past two years?</p> <p>6. What types of interventions and projects have they carried out in your camp in the past two years?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Has there been any support provided in terms of agriculture, food security, nutrition, shelter, WASH, health, or any other? ○ Have there been any distributions? What was distributed? ○ Have there been any rehabilitations and constructions? What has been rehabilitated/constructed? ○ Have there been any capacity-building activities? What topics were covered? Were any items distributed as a part of these capacity-building sessions (<i>e.g. MUAC tapes</i>)? <p>7. How many distributions took place in the last 2 years in your camp? Do you know how many camp inhabitants benefitted from different distributions?</p>

<p>What type of waste generated by humanitarian interventions can you see in your camp? (10 min)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. What types of solid waste do you encounter in the camp? Is any of it hazardous? Can you rank these types of waste from the most common to the least common? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Probe for plastic, paper, cardboard, glass, organic waste, hygienic waste (e.g. <i>diapers, pads</i>), textile, metal, construction waste, and hazardous waste. <u>Use the pictures of different types of waste.</u> 7. Where do these types of solid waste come from? (e.g. <i>market, agriculture, construction, NGO, etc.</i>) Are you able to recognize which type of waste is from activities of humanitarian organizations? 8. What types of materials are most commonly distributed by NGOs in your camp (e.g. <i>NFI kits, seeds, shelter kits...</i>)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If it is kits (WASH, shelter), probe for specific items in the kits. 9. How are these materials packaged when they are distributed? What different types of packaging materials do NGOs bring? (probe for different types of packaging) 10. What humanitarian interventions bring the most waste into your camp? (<u>Show pictures of different types of waste.</u>) 11. What type of waste is most often brought into your camp by humanitarian organizations? (<u>Show pictures of different types of waste.</u>)
<p>Where can we usually find solid waste in your camp and where is the waste from humanitarian interventions usually located? (15 min)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Where do distributions usually take place? Can you please show me the location (after our discussion)? (<u>use Kobo</u>) 6. Do the distribution recipients usually unpack the distributed materials at the site of the distribution, on the road, at home, or somewhere else? 7. When was the last distribution? 8. Can you (after our interview) practically show me what you or your camp inhabitants/management do with <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ the distributed items once they cannot be used anymore and where they are now? ○ the packaging from the last distribution and where it is now? ○ the construction waste from rehabilitations (if any)? (<u>use Kobo</u>) 9. Does most of the distribution of a) items, b) packaging, and c) construction waste end up in the camp, outside of the camp, designated dump, or is it being collected by a waste management service or transported to a waste recycling company? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Is it any different from other non-humanitarian waste? 10. Can you (after our interview) show me the location(s) where most of the waste is now, including any official and unofficial dump sites? (<u>use Kobo</u>)
<p>When does waste usually appear in your camp and how is it protected? What is the quantity and quality of waste generated in your</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Does <u>waste in general</u> appear in your community/dump sites continually or are there periods when there is more waste and less waste? If yes, when and why? 2. Does <u>humanitarian waste</u> appear in your community/dump sites continually or are there periods when there is more waste and less waste? If yes, when and why? 3. Do you know someone who knows or can estimate the amount of waste produced in your community? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If there is no such person, why? 4. Does your community/municipality have any institutions that take measures to protect your waste from destruction (e.g. <i>weather</i>) or being taken by someone or is the waste left without any supervision and protection?

<p>camp and of waste brought by NGOs? (10 min)</p>	<p>5. Is there any waste that harms the environment (air, soil, water) or causes health problems to people? How?</p>
<p>What do households do with their solid waste and who decides? Are the current practices different from the past? (20 min)</p>	<p>2. Who in your camp usually decides what to do with a) used distribution items, b) packaging from distributions, and c) other waste?</p> <p>3. What do households in your camp do with a) used distribution items, b) packaging from distributions, and c) other waste? Do the households in the camp re-use it, recycle it, compost it, throw it away, or burn it?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If your community re-uses it, how and for what? Can you show me (after the discussion)? <i>(use Kobo)</i> ○ If your community recycles it, where and how? Can you show me (after the discussion)? <i>(use Kobo)</i> ○ If your community composts it, where and how? Can you show me (after the discussion)? <i>(use Kobo)</i> ○ If your community throws it away, where? Can you show me (after the discussion)? <i>(use Kobo)</i> ○ If your community burns it, where and how often? Which type of packaging do you/your community burn? <i>(use Kobo)</i> <p>4. Do your current practices of handling solid waste differ from your tradition in the past? If yes, what are the differences?</p> <p>5. Is there any <u>solid waste</u> that your community/camp management <u>likes</u> to have? Why?</p> <p>6. Is there any <u>solid waste</u> that your community/camp management <u>doesn't like</u> to have? Why?</p> <p>7. Are there any distribution items and packaging that your community/camp management finds useful for other purposes?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Which materials are useful for which purposes? How long can you reuse it? What do you do when it is not useful anymore? <p>8. Are there any distribution items and packaging that your community/camp management does not like to receive during distributions? Why?</p>
<p>What are the waste management institutions and individuals active in the camp, how do they function and what are their responsibilities? (20 min)</p>	<p>1. Are there any camp rules for solid waste management? What are they?</p> <p>2. Are there any camp or outside-of-camp institutions/offices/NGOs/individuals (e.g. <i>informal waste pickers</i>) that are responsible for solid waste collection and management in your camp?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What are they? What are their responsibilities? Which waste do they manage? How do they function? <p>3. Does your camp have an official or unofficial dump site? Does your camp use it? Can I see it after the discussion?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Who manages it? Who manages the transportation of waste to the dump site? If there is a fee for waste collection, how much does it cost and who pays it? How do they keep records of who paid? ○ How does it look like? Is it an unprotected open space or is the waste storage space hardened, fenced, and illuminated? Is there water, sewage systems, electricity, and emission and pollution monitoring systems available? <p>4. Are there any waste recycling or composting businesses in or near your camp?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If yes, what businesses are these and what types of solid waste do they recycle or compost? ○ If yes, does your camp hand over your waste to this business for recycling or composting? How often and which type of solid waste? Does the business have the capacity to recycle and/or compost all the solid waste of the given type that your camp produces? Are there any fees applied?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If your camp hands over your waste to a recycling or composting business, how do you ensure the protection of waste from destruction (<i>rotting, severe weather conditions</i>) and from being taken by others? ○ If your camp does not use the recycling and/or composting service, why? <p>5. Are there any informal recyclers or re-users in your camp?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Who are they and how many? How do they work? Where, how often, and what type of waste do they collect? ○ What do they do with the waste? Do they re-use or recycle it by themselves or do they hand it over to a third party? Which one? What happens next? ○ What is the general perception of these informal recyclers? <p>6. Is it possible for your camp to limit the amount of solid waste it produces? If yes, what would be the possible solutions?</p> <p>7. What is the biggest challenge in terms of solid waste management for you (<i>e.g. inability to pay fees, community behavior</i>)? If possible, distinguish between waste from NGOs and other waste.</p>
<p>What are the challenges and opportunities of humanitarian waste management in your camp? (15 min)</p>	<p>9. What is the biggest challenge in terms of solid waste management for a) your camp and b) your health facility (<i>e.g. inability to pay fees, community behavior</i>)? If possible, distinguish between waste from NGOs and other waste.</p> <p>10. How can the current way of handling a) used items distributed by NGOs (when these items become waste after being used), b) packaging from items distributed by NGOs, and c) other waste (<i>e.g. construction</i>) from NGOs be improved within a) your camp?</p> <p>11. What would you need to improve the current handling of a) used items, b) packaging, and c) other waste (<i>e.g. from construction</i>) from NGOs in your camp?</p> <p>12. Are there any local actors/institutions/businesses that could contribute and provide solutions?</p> <p>13. Are there any opportunities for improving solid waste management that NGOs are not making use of?</p> <p>14. Do you know of any examples of reusing or recycling of solid waste generated by NGOs practiced in your community or other camps?</p> <p>15. Do you know/imagine any ways the bio-products or bio-technologies may improve the waste problems caused by humanitarian interventions?</p>

D3.3 – Annex 3

Bio4HUMAN KII Guide for Humanitarian SWM Needs Assessment (WP3, T3.3)

Scope: The assessment has the aim of gathering information on the types of waste in DRC and South Sudan, traditional and current methods of SWM, identification of humanitarian supply chains and leaders, and identification of the needs of humanitarian sector in SWM.

Note: This KII guide should be used for discussions separately with individual or homogeneous groups (1-3 participants) of community leaders living in rural, urban and refugee or IDP camp areas. The KII participants are leaders of communities that are direct beneficiaries of humanitarian interventions. All relevant questions in the KII have to be discussed but this doesn't mean that they have to be all posed as such. Information should emerge from the discussion. Additional questions might need to be posed to gather all relevant information.

Key Informant Interviews with community leaders (individual or homogeneous group, 1-3 participants)

Date:

Location:

Respondent's name(s):

Institution(s):

Respondent's role(s):

Age(s):

Sex(es):

Other information (disability, diversity, etc):

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QUESTIONS	Probes (not to be asked all as such but just points to be explored in the conversation if it makes sense, in <i>Italic</i> some references for the discussion)
<p>Which humanitarian organisations are active in your community and what do they do?</p> <p>(5 min)</p>	<p>8. Which humanitarian organizations have been active in your community in the past two years?</p> <p>9. What types of interventions and projects have they carried out in your community in the past two years?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Has there been any support provided in terms of agriculture, food security, nutrition, shelter, WASH, health, or any other? b. Have there been any distributions? What was distributed? c. Have there been any rehabilitations and constructions? What has been rehabilitated/constructed? d. Have there been any capacity-building activities? What topics were covered? Were any items distributed as a part of these capacity-building sessions (e.g. <i>MUAC tapes</i>)? <p>10. How many distributions took place in the last 2 years in your community? Do you know how many community members benefitted from different distributions?</p>
<p>What type of waste generated by humanitarian interventions can you see in your community?</p> <p>(10 min)</p>	<p>12. What types of solid waste do you encounter in your community? Is any of it hazardous? Can you rank these types of waste from the most common to the least common?</p>

	<p>e. Probe for plastic, paper, cardboard, glass, organic waste, hygienic waste (e.g. <i>diapers, pads</i>), textile, metal, construction waste, and hazardous waste. <u>Use the pictures of different types of waste.</u></p> <p>13. Where do these types of solid waste come from? (E.g. <i>market, agriculture, construction, NGO, etc.</i>) Are you able to recognize which type of waste is from activities of humanitarian organizations?</p> <p>14. What types of materials are most commonly distributed by NGOs in your community (e.g. <i>NFI kits, seeds, shelter kits...</i>)?</p> <p>f. If it is kits (WASH, shelter), probe for specific items in the kits.</p> <p>15. How are these materials packaged when they are distributed? What different types of packaging materials do NGOs bring? (probe for different types of packaging)</p> <p>16. What humanitarian interventions bring the most waste into your community? (<u>Show pictures of different types of waste.</u>)</p> <p>17. What type of waste is most often brought into your community by humanitarian organizations? (<u>Show pictures of different types of waste.</u>)</p>
<p><u>Where can we usually find solid waste in your community and where is the waste from humanitarian interventions usually located?</u></p> <p>(15 min)</p>	<p>11. Where do distributions usually take place? Can you please show me the location (after our discussion)? (<u>use Kobo</u>)</p> <p>12. Do the distribution recipients usually unpack the distributed materials at the site of the distribution, on the road, at home, or somewhere else?</p> <p>13. When was the last distribution?</p>

	<p>14. Can you (after our interview) practically show me what you or your community does with</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> g. the distributed items once they cannot be used anymore and where they are now? h. the packaging from the last distribution and where it is now? i. the construction waste from rehabilitations (if any)? (<i>use Kobo</i>) <p>15. Does most of the distribution of a) items, b) packaging, and c) construction waste end up in the community, outside of the community, designated community dump, or is it being collected by a waste management service or transported to a waste recycling company?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> j. Is it any different from other non-humanitarian waste? <p>16. Can you (after our interview) show me the location(s) where most of the waste is now, including any official and unofficial dump sites? (<i>use Kobo</i>)</p>
<p><u>When does waste usually appear in your community and how is it protected? What is the <u>quantity</u> and <u>quality</u> of waste generated in your community and of waste brought by NGOs?</u></p> <p>(10 min)</p>	<p>6. Does <u>waste in general</u> appear in your community/dump sites continually or are there periods when there is more waste and less waste? If yes, when and why?</p> <p>7. Does <u>humanitarian waste</u> appear in your community/dump sites continually or are there periods when there is more waste and less waste? If yes, when and why?</p> <p>8. Do you know someone who knows or can estimate the amount of waste produced in your community?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> k. If there is no such person, why?

	<p>9. Does your community/municipality have any institutions that take measures to protect your waste from destruction (e.g. <i>weather</i>) or being taken by someone or is the waste left without any supervision and protection?</p> <p>10. Is there any waste that harms the environment (air, soil, water) or causes health problems to people? How?</p>
<p>What are the types of waste produced by HFs and obtained by HFs form NGOs?</p> <p>(5 min)</p>	<p>1. What types of solid waste does your health facility produce? What hazardous solid waste is produced there?</p> <p>2. What type of materials does your HF receive from NGOs during distributions (e.g. Plumpynut, F75, F100, medication, sanitation materials, WASH materials)? What type of rehabilitation (if any) were received?</p> <p>3. In the past 2 years, have there been other materials distributed to the community through your HF? If yes, which ones?</p>
<p>What do households do with their solid waste and who decides? Are the current practices different from the past?</p> <p>(20 min)</p>	<p>9. Who in your <u>community</u> usually decides what to do with a) used distribution items, b) packaging from distributions, and c) other waste?</p> <p>10. What do households in your community do with a) used distribution items, b) packaging from distributions, and c) other waste? Do your community households re-use it, recycle it, compost it, throw it away, or burn it?</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">l. If your community re-uses it, how and for what? Can you show me (after the discussion)? (<i>use Kobo</i>)</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">m. If your community recycles it, where and how? Can you show me (after the discussion)? (<i>use Kobo</i>)</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> n. If your community composts it, where and how? Can you show me (after the discussion)? <i>(use Kobo)</i> o. If your community throws it away, where? Can you show me (after the discussion)? <i>(use Kobo)</i> p. If your community burns it, where and how often? Which type of packaging do you/your community burn? <i>(use Kobo)</i> <p>11. Do your current practices of handling solid waste differ from your tradition in the past? If yes, what are the differences?</p> <p>12. Is there any <u>solid waste</u> that your community <u>likes</u> to have? Why?</p> <p>13. Is there any <u>solid waste</u> that your community <u>doesn't like</u> to have? Why?</p> <p>14. Are there any distribution items and packaging that your community finds useful for other purposes?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> q. Which materials are useful for which purposes? How long can you reuse it? What do you do when it is not useful anymore? <p>15. Are there any distribution items and packaging that your community does not like to receive during distributions? Why?</p>
<p>What are the waste management institutions and individuals active in communities, how do they function and what are their responsibilities?</p> <p>(20 min)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Are there any community rules for solid waste management? What are they? 2. Are there any community institutions/offices/NGOs/individuals (<i>e.g. informal waste pickers</i>) that are responsible for solid waste collection and management in your community?

- r. What are they? What are their responsibilities? Which waste do they manage? How do they function?
3. Does your community have an official or unofficial dump site? Do you/your community use it? Can I see it after the discussion?
 - s. Who manages it? Who manages the transportation of waste to the dump site? If there is a fee for waste collection, how much does it cost and who pays it? How do they keep records of who paid?
 - t. How does it look like? Is it an unprotected open space or is the waste storage space hardened, fenced, and illuminated? Is there water, sewage system, electricity, and emission and pollution monitoring systems available?
4. Are there any waste recycling or composting businesses in or near your community?
 - u. If yes, what businesses are these, and what types of solid waste do they recycle or compost?
 - v. If yes, does your community hand over your waste to this business for recycling or composting? How often and which type of solid waste? Does the business have the capacity to recycle and/or compost all the solid waste of the given type that your community produces? Are there any fees applied?
 - w. If your community hands over your waste to a recycling or composting business, how do you ensure the protection of waste from destruction (*rotting, severe weather conditions*) and from being taken by others?
 - x. If your community does not use the recycling and/or composting service, why?
5. Are there any informal recyclers or re-users in your community?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> y. Who are they and how many? How do they work? Where, how often, and what type of waste do they collect? z. What do they do with the waste? Do they re-use or recycle it by themselves or do they hand it over to a third party? Which one? What happens next? aa. What is the general perception of these informal recyclers? 6. Is it possible for your community to limit the amount of solid waste it produces? If yes, what would be the possible solutions? 7. What is the biggest challenge in terms of solid waste management for you (e.g. <i>inability to pay fees, community behavior</i>)? If possible, distinguish between waste from NGOs and other waste.
<p>How is solid waste managed in your health facilities, what are the main practices and who are the key actors?</p> <p>(15 min)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What do your health facility and community do with a) the waste produced by the health facility and b) obtained from NGOs (including distributions and rehabilitations)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> bb. Are there any specific solid waste management standards that are applied to the health facility? What are they? cc. Are there informal community solid waste recyclers/re-users that handpick/collect the HF waste and reuse/recycle/resell the waste? If yes, who are these recyclers/re-users, and what type of waste and how often do they pick/collect? 2. Is there a community waste management service that collects the waste the HF produces? What is the name of this service? How often does it collect the waste? Does it collect all types of waste (incl. hazardous waste) or only a specific type? 3. Is any type of solid waste handed over to an official recycling business?

	<p>dd. If yes, which type of solid waste is handed to this business? What is the name of this business? Are there any fees applied? Who is responsible for the transport of the waste?</p> <p>4. Is your current way of handling the solid waste you produce and receive from NGOs different from the traditional practices in the past? If yes, how?</p> <p>5. Is it possible that your HF limits the solid waste that you produce? What would be the solutions?</p>
<p>What are the challenges and opportunities of humanitarian waste management in your community?</p> <p>(15 min)</p>	<p>16. What is the biggest challenge in terms of solid waste management for a) your community and b) your health facility (e.g. <i>inability to pay fees, community behavior</i>)? If possible, distinguish between waste from NGOs and other waste.</p> <p>17. How can the current way of handling a) used items distributed by NGOs (when these items become waste after being used), b) packaging from items distributed by NGOs, and c) other waste (e.g. construction) from NGOs be improved within a) your community and b) your health facility?</p> <p>18. What would you need to improve the current handling of a) used items, b) packaging, and c) other waste (e.g. from construction) from NGOs in a) your community and b) your health facility?</p> <p>19. Are there any local actors/institutions/businesses that could contribute and provide solutions?</p> <p>20. Are there any opportunities for improving solid waste management that NGOs are not making use of?</p> <p>21. Do you know of any examples of reusing or recycling of solid waste generated by NGOs practiced in your community?</p>

	22. Do you know/imagine any ways the bio-products or bio-technologies may improve the waste problems caused by humanitarian interventions?
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D3.3 – Annex 4

Bio4HUMAN KII Guide for Humanitarian SWM Needs Assessment (WP3, T3.3)

Scope: The assessment has the aim of gathering information on the types of waste in DRC and South Sudan, traditional and current methods of SWM, identification of humanitarian supply chains and leaders, and identification of the needs of the humanitarian sector in SWM.

Note: This KII guide should be used for discussions separately with individual or homogeneous groups (1-3 participants) of province/country representatives in urban areas. The KII participants are representatives of a) municipalities that are direct beneficiaries of humanitarian interventions or b) cities that are hubs for SWM stakeholders, including government, businesses, and academia. All relevant questions in the KII have to be discussed but this doesn't mean that they have to be all posed as such. Information should emerge from the discussion. Additional questions might need to be posed to gather all relevant information.

Key Informant Interviews with government (province, national) representatives and academia (individual or homogeneous group, 1-3 participants)

Date:

Location:

Respondent's name(s):

Institution(s):

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Respondent's role(s):

Age(s):

Sex(es):

Other information (disability, diversity, etc):

PIN/PAH staff conducting the interview:

QUESTIONS	Probes (not to be asked all as such but just points to be explored in the conversation if it makes sense, in <i>Italic</i> some references for the discussion)
<p>Which humanitarian organizations are active in your province/country and what do they do? (10 min)</p>	<p>11. Which humanitarian organizations have been active in your province/country in the past two years?</p> <p>12. What types of interventions and projects have they carried out in your province/country in the past two years?</p> <p>13. Is any local or international NGO working on solid waste management? If yes, can you explain what they are doing and how is the government involved?</p>
<p>What is the solid waste impact of humanitarian organizations in your province/country? (10 min)</p>	<p>18. Do you have any discussions with international NGOs about the environmental impact of their operations in your province/country?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Do you have any requirements or legislation regarding solid waste impact and/or management that NGOs have to follow? <p>19. Do you monitor the solid waste production and/or impact of humanitarian NGOs?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Do you have information about how much of what type of solid waste is brought in/created by operations and activities (distributions, constructions) of humanitarian NGOs in your province/country? o If yes, can you please share with me your findings and reports? <p>20. If you do not monitor nor discuss the solid waste impact of NGOs in your province/country, can you tell me why?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Is it not a priority/concern of the province/country? Does the province/country have insufficient capacities (staff, budget, will) to tackle this issue?

<p>What are the current practices, requirements and initiatives regarding (humanitarian) solid waste management in your province/country? (15 min)</p>	<p>17. What is the solid waste management legislation in your country? What are the guidelines for waste storage, protection, and management?</p> <p>18. What are the current practices in your province/country regarding the disposal of humanitarian waste (including packaging, distribution, and construction waste)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Do they differ from practices concerning the disposal of other (“normal”) waste? If yes, how? ○ Do you have any best/worst practices to highlight? <p>19. Does your province/country have any requirements regarding disposal/reuse/repurposing of waste? If yes, what are they?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Is waste being shipped elsewhere for disposal? If so, where? ○ Are there practices particular to a specific type of (humanitarian) packaging waste (e.g. plastic, carton, fabric, wood) or a specific product (e.g. plastic containers, wood pallets, food wrappers, etc.)? <p>20. Do you have any solid waste management initiatives driven by the government, NGOs, or businesses? If so, what are they?</p>
<p>What are the waste management institutions and individuals active in your province/country? How do they function and what are their responsibilities? (20 min)</p>	<p>8. Who are the entities and institutions active in the SWM value chain in your province/country? (e.g. dump sites, recycling or composting businesses, informal recyclers)</p> <p>9. What are their roles and responsibilities (collection, transport, storage, recycling, reuse, composting)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Which waste do they manage? ○ How do they function? ○ Are there any fees applied? How does it work? How do they keep records of who pays? ○ How do they protect waste from destruction or rotting or from being taken by others? ○ Are they able to manage all the waste that your province/country produces? ○ If you do not have/use recycling and/or composting services, why? <p>10. Is it possible for your province/country to limit the amount of solid waste it produces? If yes, what would be the possible solutions?</p>
<p>What are the challenges and opportunities of humanitarian waste management in your province/country? (25 min)</p>	<p>23. What is the biggest challenge in terms of solid waste management for your province/country at this moment (e.g. <i>inability to pay fees, community behavior, lack of machinery and means of transport</i>)? If possible, distinguish between waste from NGOs and other waste.</p> <p>24. How can the current way of handling (humanitarian) waste be improved within your province/country?</p> <p>25. What would you need to improve the current handling of (humanitarian) waste in your province/country?</p> <p>26. Are there any local actors/institutions/businesses that could contribute and provide solutions? Are there any actors that are already offering bio-based solutions?</p>

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| | <p>27. Do you know/imagine any ways the bio-products or bio-technologies may improve the waste problems caused by humanitarian interventions?</p> <p>28. Are there any opportunities for improving solid waste management that NGOs/provinces/country are not making use of?</p> <p>29. Do you know of any examples of reusing or recycling of solid waste generated by NGOs practiced in your province/country?</p> |
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D3.3 – Annex 5

Bio4HUMAN KII Guide for Humanitarian SWM Needs Assessment (WP3, T3.3)

Scope: The assessment has the aim of gathering information on the types of waste in DRC and South Sudan, traditional and current methods of SWM, identification of humanitarian supply chains and leaders, and identification of needs of the humanitarian sector in SWM.

Note: This KII guide should be used for discussions separately with individual or homogeneous groups (1-3 participants) of health facility staff living in rural, urban, and refugee or IDP camp areas. The KII participants are staff of health facilities that are direct beneficiaries of humanitarian interventions or are used as intermediaries for humanitarian interventions in their communities. All relevant questions in the KII have to be discussed but this doesn't mean that they have to be all posed as such. Information should emerge from the discussion. Additional questions might need to be posed to gather all relevant information.

Key Informant Interviews with health facility staff (individual or homogeneous group, 1-3 participants)

Date:

Location:

Respondent's name(s):

Institution(s):

Respondent's role(s):

Age(s):

Sex(es):

Other information (disability, diversity, etc):

QUESTIONS	Probes (not to be asked all as such but just points to be explored in the conversation if it makes sense, in <i>Italic</i> some references for the discussion)
<p>Which humanitarian organisations are active in your community and what do they do? (5 min)</p>	<p>14. Which humanitarian organizations have been active in your community in the past two years?</p> <p>15. What types of interventions and projects have they carried out in your community in the past two years?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Has there been any support provided in terms of agriculture, food security, nutrition, shelter, WASH, health, or any other? ○ Have there been any distributions? What was distributed? ○ Have there been any rehabilitations and constructions? What has been rehabilitated/constructed? ○ Have there been any capacity-building activities? What topics were covered? Were any items distributed as a part of these capacity-building sessions (<i>e.g. MUAC tapes</i>)? <p>16. How many distributions took place in the last 2 years in your community? Do you know how many community members benefitted from different distributions?</p>
<p>What are the types of waste produced by HFs and obtained by HFs from NGOs?</p>	<p>4. What types of solid waste does your health facility produce? What hazardous solid waste is produced there? <i>Use the pictures of different types of waste.</i></p>

<p>(15 min)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. What type of materials does your HF receive from NGOs during distributions (e.g. Plumpynut, F75, F100, medication, sanitation materials, WASH materials)? 6. What types of rehabilitation (if any) done by NGOs took place in your health facility? 7. In the past 2 years, have there been other materials distributed to the community through your HF (e.g. <i>WASH kits, shelter kits, MUAC tapes...</i>)? If yes, which ones? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If it is kits (WASH, shelter), probe for specific items in the kits. 8. What is the packaging material usually used by NGOs during distributions in/to your HF? (<i>Show pictures of different types of waste.</i>) Can you show me? (<i>use Kobo</i>) 9. What humanitarian interventions bring the most waste into your HF? (<i>Show pictures of different types of waste.</i>) 10. What type of waste is most often brought into your HF by humanitarian organizations? (<i>Show pictures of different types of waste.</i>)
<p><u>Where can we usually find solid waste in your HF and where is the waste from humanitarian interventions usually located?</u> (20 min)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 21. Where do you usually store your waste? Can you show me? (<i>use Kobo</i>) 22. Where do distributions aimed at the community (if any) usually take place in your HF? Can you please show me the location (after our discussion)? (<i>use Kobo</i>) 23. When was the last distribution? 24. Do the distribution recipients from the community usually unpack the distributed materials in your HF if distributions take place in your HF? If yes, can you show me where? (<i>use Kobo</i>) 25. Does the <u>packaging material</u> from distributions to the community done through your HF usually stay at the HF premises or is it taken home by the beneficiaries? If it stays in the HF, can you show me where? (<i>use Kobo</i>) 26. Do the <u>distributed items</u> from distributions done to the community through your HF usually stay in the HF? If yes, can you show me where? (<i>use Kobo</i>) 27. Can you practically show me what your HF does with <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ the items distributed by NGOs (to or through the HF) once they cannot be used anymore and where they are now? ○ the packaging from the last distribution (to or through the HF) and where it is now? ○ the construction waste from rehabilitations (if any) done by NGOs in your HF? (<i>use Kobo</i>) 28. Does most of the distribution a) items, b) packaging, and c) construction waste end up in the HF premises, HF incinerator, community, outside of the community, designated community dump, or is it being collected by a waste management service or transported to a waste recycling company? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Is it any different from other non-humanitarian waste? 29. Can you show me the location(s) where most of the waste is now, including any official and unofficial dump sites? (<i>use Kobo</i>)

<p><u>When does waste usually appear in your HF and how is it protected? What is the quantity and quality of waste generated in your HF and of waste brought by NGOs?</u> (15 min)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 11. Do you produce similar amounts of waste continuously or are there periods when you produce more and less waste? If yes, when? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Do you have records of how many different types of waste are produced in your HF per month/year? Can you share these records with me? ○ If not, why don't you have this information? 12. Does <u>humanitarian waste</u> appear in your HF sites continually or are there periods when there is more waste and less waste? If yes, when and why? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Do you have records of how many items/boxes of different support (Plumpynut, medication, etc.) you have received from NGOs in the past 2 years? Can you share these records with me? ○ If not, why you do not have these records? 13. Does your HF take any measures to protect your waste from disintegration/destruction (e.g. <i>weather, rotting</i>) or being taken by someone, or is the waste left without any supervision and protection? (<u>use Kobo</u>) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If yes, what measures do you take for which type of waste? 14. Do you produce any waste that harms the environment (air, soil, water) or causes health problems to people? How? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Do you take any measures to prevent the negative impact? If yes, what measures do you take? (<u>use Kobo</u>)
<p><u>How is solid waste managed in your HF, what are the main practices and who are the key actors?</u> (20 min)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. What does your health facility/community do with a) the waste produced by the health facility and b) obtained from NGOs (including distributions and rehabilitation)? (<u>use Kobo</u>) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Are there any specific solid waste management standards that are applied to the health facility? What are they? ○ Does the HF have an incinerator? Which type of solid waste is incinerated? How often? ○ Which type of solid waste is burned (on an open fire)? Where? How often? ○ Which type of solid waste is thrown away? Where? ○ Which type of solid waste is re-used? How and for how long? What happens after it is no longer fit to be re-used? ○ Are there informal community solid waste recyclers/re-users that handpick/collect the HF waste and reuse/recycle/resell the waste? If yes, who are these recyclers/re-users, and what type of waste and how often do they pick/collect? Do you sell them waste for a fee? How much? 7. Is there a community waste management service that collects the waste the HF produces? What is the name of this service? How often does it collect the waste? Does it collect all types of waste (incl. hazardous waste) or only a specific type? Is there any fee you have to pay? How much? 8. Is any type of solid waste handed over to an official recycling business? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If yes, which type of solid waste is handed to this business? What is the name of this business? Are there any fees applied? Who is responsible for the transport of the waste?

	<p>9. Is your current way of handling the solid waste you produce and receive from NGOs different from the traditional practices in the past? If yes, how?</p> <p>10. Is there any a) solid waste, or b) distributed items and their packaging that your HF <u>likes</u> to have/finds useful for other purposes? Why?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Which materials are useful for which purpose? How long can you reuse it? What do you do when it is not useful anymore? <p>11. Is there any a) solid waste, or b) distributed items and their packaging that your HF <u>doesn't like</u> to have/doesn't find useful for other purposes? Why?</p> <p>12. Is it possible that your HF limits the solid waste that you produce? What would be the solutions?</p>
<p>What are the challenges and opportunities of humanitarian waste management in your HF? (15 min)</p>	<p>30. What is the biggest challenge in terms of solid waste management for your HF (e.g. <i>inability to pay fees, community behavior</i>)? If possible, distinguish between waste from NGOs and other waste.</p> <p>31. How can the current way of handling a) used items distributed by NGOs (when these items become waste after being used), b) packaging from items distributed by NGOs, and c) other waste (e.g. construction) from NGOs be improved within your health facility?</p> <p>32. What would you need to improve the current handling of a) used items, b) packaging, and c) other waste (e.g. from construction) from NGOs in your health facility?</p> <p>33. Are there any local actors/institutions/businesses that could contribute and provide solutions?</p> <p>34. Are there any opportunities for improving solid waste management that NGOs are not making use of?</p> <p>35. Do you know of any examples of reusing or recycling of solid waste generated by NGOs practiced in your community?</p> <p>36. Do you know/imagine any ways the bio-products or bio-technologies may improve the waste problems caused by humanitarian interventions?</p>

D3.3 – Annex 6

Bio4HUMAN KII Guide for Humanitarian SWM Needs Assessment (WP3, T3.3)

Scope: The assessment has the aim of gathering information on the types of waste in DRC and South Sudan, traditional and current methods of SWM, identification of humanitarian supply chains and leaders, and identification of needs of the humanitarian sector in SWM.

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Note: This KII guide should be used for discussions separately with individual or homogeneous groups (1-3 participants) of humanitarian representatives active in DRC or South Sudan. The KII participants are representatives of a) NGOs conducting humanitarian interventions or b) clusters, and c) UN agencies. All relevant questions in the KII have to be discussed but this doesn't mean that they have to be all posed as such. Information should emerge from the discussion. Additional questions might need to be posed to gather all relevant information.

Key Informant Interviews with humanitarian representatives (individual or homogeneous group, 1-3 participants)

Date:

Location:

Respondent's name(s):

Organization:

Respondent's role(s):

Age(s):

Sex(es):

Other information (disability, diversity, etc.):

PIN/PAH staff conducting the interview:

QUESTIONS	Probes (not to be asked all as such but just points to be explored in the conversation if it makes sense, in <i>Italic</i> some references for the discussion)
Types and quantity of waste produced by organization in project/program implementation (20 min)	1. What type of interventions (sectors) do you implement in DRC / South Sudan and in which locations? 2. What waste do you produce by your activities? Do you have a list of these? Please provide data on quantity, type, and volume as available (<i>e.g. number of items shipped, amount of waste generated, tons of plastic/cardboard/other packaging waste that may be produced</i>)

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	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. What are the largest sources of packaging waste, construction waste or other potential sources of solid wastes for your organization throughout the supply chain (e.g., production, transportation, distribution construction) or its use? 4. Do you have in place a mechanism to measure the quantities and types of waste you produce by your activities (by-product)? How do you measure it? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Are you able to estimate the quantity of the waste your activities produce e.g. yearly? ○ If you don't have this information, can you tell me why? What are the main obstacles to measuring waste? 5. What would you need to improve in your current solid waste impact on target communities?
SWM in your organization (20 min)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Do you have your own SWM policies/SOPs or do you have SWM (project/programme-level) strategy as part of your SOPs/CP strategies? If yes, do you implement it? If yes, would you be able to share them with us? 2. Are you interested in SWM? Do you implement any SWM or related projects/activities? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If yes, what are these projects and where are they? Do you have any partners? Can you share any reports? ○ If yes, what type(s) of waste do they address? How many tons of waste do these interventions tackle per month/year? How is the solid waste managed by these interventions (recycling, re-usage, composting)? ○ If yes, do you focus on waste recovery?¹ ○ Do you pool waste management (waste sharing) with another organization? ○ If no, what are the main issues hindering your active involvement in SWM in your targeted areas? (e.g. internal organization issues, such as sustainable SWM not priority, lack of capacity, etc.; or SWM not priority because it cannot work without proper involvement of local government who are not interested, etc.) 3. Do you think you have enough internal SWM expertise? 4. Do you have enough budget to do SWM? 5. Are you able to fulfill the main Sphere SWM standards? If not, what are the main challenges for you to fulfill the SPHERE main SWM standards? 6. Do you think SWM is your responsibility? 7. Would you say you give high/medium/low priority to SWM?

¹ Waste recovery is part of the concept of 'circular economy', which implies improving consumer behaviour on the one hand, and adapting the offer proposed by economic actors on the other. This suggests more sustainable purchasing concepts and the design of products in a responsible manner.

	<p>8. Are you currently conducting/have you conducted any assessment focused on SWM or humanitarian packaging? Have you assessed waste streams and issues before the implementation of your humanitarian response/start of projects? Or have you conducted an assessment on any other related issue?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If yes: what products/supply chains are being assessed? ○ Is it possible to share the assessment?
<p>Sustainable/responsible procurement and supply strategy (20 min)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Where do you get your core humanitarian inputs for distribution or construction? Do you have international or local supply chains? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Are you able to estimate what is the % of international vs. local sourcing? ○ From where do you source the most common packaged products or other potential sources of waste that you distribute? Please list if possible the products sourced from each region, as well as the source country. 2. Does your supply chain strategy consider the following? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Using environmental criteria in the selection of materials and in construction, and including these in procurement practices ○ Requiring environmental labels and standards for key products ○ Extending responsibility in the supply chain to include all sub-suppliers 3. Do you implement any initiatives within the sustainable/responsible procurement? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If not, why not? (<i>e.g. internal org issues, such as sustainable SWM not priority, lack of capacity etc.; or SWM not priority because it cannot work without proper involvement of local government who are not interested</i>) 4. How can your approach to solid waste in your operations and activities be improved? In your opinion, what are the easy wins in your organization relating to minimizing the environmental impacts of waste? Do you see any opportunities for improving your SWM that are not being utilized? 5. Is procurement the best place to start the systemic changes, e.g. for waste minimization/avoidance/place where to start integrating innovative solutions? If not, where should we start to minimize humanitarian solid waste?
<p>What are the environmental impacts of main materials and supplies used by your organisation? (5 min)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Do you map the environmental impacts (<i>chemicals, energy, waste, resources, air pollution, water</i>) of the main materials and supplies used within your operations (using a life-cycle approach, accompanied by an overview of suppliers and sub-suppliers)? 2. Do you use the results of the mapping to prioritize efforts based on environmental impacts and opportunities and/or spheres of influence?
<p>Collaboration with local stakeholders</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the local methods of waste disposal and SWM?

(15 min)	<p>(10 Any best or worst practices to highlight?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Do you know and/or collaborate with the local stakeholders (waste generators, waste processors, formal and informal agencies, non-governmental organisations, and financing institutions) involved in SWM? Who are they? 3. How would you rate the collaboration with local authorities/service providers when trying to integrate SWM into already existing systems and infrastructure? 4. Are there any local actors that you know of or work with that could contribute to SWM solutions? Who are they? 5. Are you aware of any ongoing SWM assessments conducted by other organizations or institutions? 6. Are there any cultural aspects for SWM that we should know about that could influence different types of SWM - re-using, recycling, composting, throwing away, or burning?
<p>SWM – bio-based solutions (5 min)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What do you think is the most pressing issue related to SWM in the humanitarian sector? 2. Do you see bio-based products/systems as a solution for sustainable SWM in humanitarian interventions? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ E.g. bio-based production/packaging solutions (by the suppliers of the products) or bio – based technologies and systems that ensure the natural biodegradation of residues or their easy disposal or bio-based technologies offering further use by the local community, e.g., for fertilizers or biofuel production?

D3.3 - Annex 7

Bio4HUMAN KII Guide for Humanitarian SWM Needs Assessment (WP3 T3.3)

Scope: The assessment has the aim of gathering information on the types of waste in DRC and South Sudan, traditional and current methods of SWM, identification of humanitarian supply chains and leaders, and identification of needs of the humanitarian sector in SWM.

Note: This KII guide should be used for discussions separately with individual or homogeneous group (1-3 participants) of representatives of EU-based humanitarian organizations. The KII participants are representatives of a) EU-based humanitarian organizations and b) UN agencies. All relevant questions in the KII have to be discussed but this doesn't mean that they have to be all posed as such. Information should emerge from the discussion. Additional questions might need to be posed to gather all relevant information.

Key Informant Interviews with EU-based humanitarian organisations (UN agencies/INGOs) (individual or homogeneous group, 1-3 participants)

Date:

Location:

Respondent's name(s):

Respondent's organisation:

Respondent's role(s):

Age(s):

Sex(es):

Other information (disability, diversity, etc):

QUESTIONS	Probes (not to be asked all as such but just points to be explored in the conversation if it makes sense, in <i>Italic</i> some references for the discussion)
SWM at your organisation (10 in)	2. Does your organisation have an SWM planning framework? Do you implement it? 3. Do you pool waste management (waste sharing) in some countries where you work? 4. Do you focus on waste recovery? ²

1. ² Waste recovery is part of the concept of 'circular economy', which implies improving consumer behaviour on the one hand, and adapting the offer proposed by economic actors on the other. This suggests more sustainable purchasing concepts and the design of products in a responsible manner.

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	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Are you currently conducting/have you conducted any assessment focused on SWM? or humanitarian packaging? Or any other related issue? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If yes: what products/supply chains are being assessed? ○ Is it possible to share? 6. Are you aware of any ongoing assessments by other organizations? 7. Could you recommend any key publications/literature (except the WREC) we should review as we begin this work? 8. What do you think is the most pressing issue related to SWM in the humanitarian sector? Or What is hampering you from implementing sustainable SWM within your projects” 9. In your opinion, what are the easy wins in your organization relating to minimizing the environmental impacts of waste?
SWM – bio-based solutions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Do you see bio-based products/systems as a solution for sustainable SWM? E.g. bio-based production/packaging solutions (by the suppliers of the products) or bio – based technologies and systems that ensure the natural biodegradation of residues or their easy disposal or bio-based technologies offering further use by the local community, e.g., for fertilisers or biofuel production)? 4. Is it something else? For example: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) internal org issues, such as sustainable SWM not priority, lack of capacity, etc.) b) SWM is not a priority because it cannot work without the proper involvement of local governments which are not interested.
Sustainable/responsible procurement (10 in)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Do you implement something else within the sustainable/responsible procurement? 2. Is procurement the best place to start the systemic changes, e.g. for waste minimization/avoidance/place where to start integrating innovative solutions?
Types and quantity of waste produced by organization (15 min)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What waste do you produce by your activities? Do you have a list of these? Please provide data on quantity, type, and volume as available (e.g. number of items shipped, amount of waste generated, tons of plastic/cardboard/other packaging waste that may be produced) 2. Do you have in place (in-country programs) mechanisms to measure the waste you produce by your activities (by-product)? How do you measure it? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If you don ’ t have this information, can you tell why? What are the main obstacles to measuring waste?

Environmental impacts of main materials and supplies used by your organisation? (20min)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Do you map the environmental impacts (chemicals, energy, waste, resources, air pollution, water) of the main materials and supplies used within your operations using a life-cycle approach, accompanied by an overview of suppliers and sub-suppliers? 3. Do you use the results of the mapping to prioritize efforts based on environmental impacts and opportunities and/or sphere of influence?
Supply chain (25min)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Does your supply chain strategy consider the following? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Using environmental criteria in the selection of materials and in construction, and including these in procurement practices ○ Requiring environmental/social labels and standards for key products ○ Extending responsibility in the supply chain to include all sub-suppliers 2. Do you source locally/regionally? Are you able to estimate what is the % of international vs local sourcing? 3. From where do you source the most common packaged products or other potential sources of waste that you distribute? Please list if possible, the products sourced from each region, as well as the source country.
Waste packaging	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the current disposal practices for packaging waste in humanitarian contexts? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Any best/worst practices to highlight? 2. Do you have any requirements on the disposal/reuse/repurposing of packaging waste? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Is waste being shipped elsewhere for disposal? If so, where? ○ Are there practices particular to a type of humanitarian packaging waste (e.g., plastic, paper, wood) or a specific product (e.g., wood pallets, plastic containers or wrap, food wrappers)? 3. Examples of biodegradable packaging? Reusing packaging waste or reverse logistics? Minimizing packaging waste? 4. Who is in the waste management space in developing countries with ongoing humanitarian emergencies? What practices do they use to reduce uncontrolled disposal (i.e., litter) of humanitarian aid waste? 5. Are there any NGOs or organizations we should know about working in this space? 6. Are any governments driving activities? If so, which countries and which government departments? For example, Uganda/Kenya has recent plastics bans. 7. What are the largest sources of packaging waste or other potential sources of waste for your organization throughout the supply chain (e.g., production, transportation, or distribution) or its use?

Waste generation	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. What are the general locations from which packaging products or potential wastes are being sourced (e.g., US, Europe, etc.)?2. Do you have any activity-specific data? E.g.:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Number of items shipped to these areas?○ Amount of waste generated?○ Tons of plastic/cardboard/other waste/packaging waste collected?3. Do you characterize waste differently (e.g., numbers of containers)?
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D3.3 – Annex 8

Bio4HUMAN KII Guide for Humanitarian SWM Needs Assessment (WP3, T3.3)

Scope: The assessment has the aim of gathering information on the types of waste in DRC and South Sudan, traditional and current methods of SWM, identification of humanitarian supply chains and leaders, and identification of needs of the humanitarian sector in SWM.

Note: This KII guide should be used for discussions separately with individual or homogeneous groups (1-3 participants) of municipality representatives in urban areas. The KII participants are representatives of a) municipalities that are direct beneficiaries of humanitarian interventions or b) cities that are hubs for SWM stakeholders, including government, businesses, and academia. All relevant questions in the KII have to be discussed but this doesn't mean that they have to be all posed as such. Information should emerge from the discussion. Additional questions might need to be posed to gather all relevant information.

Key Informant Interviews with local government (e.g. municipality, payam, etc.) representatives (individual or homogeneous group, 1-3 participants)

Date:

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Location:

Respondent's name(s):

Institution(s):

Respondent's role(s):

Age(s):

Sex(es):

Other information (disability, diversity, etc):

PIN/PAH staff conducting the interview:

QUESTIONS	Probes (not to be asked all as such but just points to be explored in the conversation if it makes sense, in <i>Italic</i> some references for the discussion)
<p>Which humanitarian organizations are active in your municipality and what do they do? (10 min)</p>	<p>17. Which humanitarian organizations have been active in your municipality in the past two years? 18. What types of interventions and projects have they carried out in your municipality in the past two years? 19. Is any local or international NGO working on solid waste management? If yes, can you explain what they are doing and how is the municipality involved?</p>
<p>What is the solid waste impact of humanitarian organizations in your municipality? (10 min)</p>	<p>21. Do you have any discussions with international NGOs about the environmental impact of their operations in your municipality? ○ Do you have any requirements regarding solid waste impact and/or management that NGOs have to follow? 22. Do you monitor the solid waste production and/or impact of humanitarian NGOs? ○ Do you have information about how much of what type of solid waste is brought in/created by operations and activities (distributions, constructions) of humanitarian NGOs in your municipality? ○ If yes, can you please share with me your findings? 23. If you do not monitor nor discuss the solid waste impact of NGOs in your municipality, can you tell me why?</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Is it not a priority/concern of the municipality? Does the municipality have insufficient capacities (staff, budget, will) to tackle this issue?
<p>What are the current practices, requirements and initiatives regarding (humanitarian) solid waste management in your municipality? (15 min)</p>	<p>30. What is the solid waste management legislation in your country? What are the guidelines for waste storage, protection, and management?</p> <p>31. What are the current practices in your municipality regarding the disposal of humanitarian waste (including packaging, distribution, and construction waste)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Do they differ from practices concerning the disposal of other (“normal”) waste? If yes, how? ○ Do you have any best/worst practices to highlight? <p>32. Does your municipality have any requirements regarding disposal/reuse/repurposing of waste? If yes, what are they?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Is waste being shipped elsewhere for disposal? If so, where? ○ Are there practices particular to a specific type of (humanitarian) packaging waste (e.g. plastic, carton, fabric, wood) or a specific product (e.g. plastic containers, wood pallets, food wrappers, etc.)? <p>33. Do you have any solid waste management initiatives driven by the government, NGOs, or businesses? If so, what are they?</p>
<p>What are the waste management institutions and individuals active in your municipality? How do they function and what are their responsibilities? (20 min)</p>	<p>11. Who are the entities and institutions active in the SWM value chain in your municipality? (e.g. dump sites, recycling or composting businesses, informal recyclers)</p> <p>12. What are their roles and responsibilities (collection, transport, storage, recycling, reuse, composting)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Which waste do they manage? ○ How do they function? ○ Are there any fees applied? How does it work? How do they keep records of who pays? ○ How do they protect waste from destruction or rotting or from being taken by others? ○ Are they able to manage all the waste that your municipality produces? ○ If your community does not use the recycling and/or composting service, why? <p>13. Is it possible for your municipality to limit the amount of solid waste it produces? If yes, what would be the possible solutions?</p>
<p>What are the challenges and opportunities of humanitarian waste management in your municipality? (25 min)</p>	<p>37. What is the biggest challenge in terms of solid waste management for your municipality at this moment (e.g. <i>inability to pay fees, community behavior</i>)? If possible, distinguish between waste from NGOs and other waste.</p> <p>38. How can the current way of handling (humanitarian) waste be improved within your municipality?</p> <p>39. What would you need to improve the current handling of (humanitarian) waste in your municipality?</p> <p>40. Are there any local actors/institutions/businesses that could contribute and provide solutions? Are there any actors that are already offering bio-based solutions?</p>

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| | <ol style="list-style-type: none">41. Do you know/imagine any ways the bio-products or bio-technologies may improve the waste problems caused by humanitarian interventions?42. Are there any opportunities for improving solid waste management that NGOs/municipality are not making use of?43. Do you know of any examples of reusing or recycling of solid waste generated by NGOs practiced in your municipality? |
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D3.3 – Annex 9

Bio4HUMAN FGD Guide for Humanitarian SWM Needs Assessment (WP3, T3.3)

Scope: The assessment has the aim of gathering information on the types of waste in DRC and South Sudan, traditional and current methods of SWM, identification of humanitarian supply chains and leaders, and identification of needs of the humanitarian sector in SWM.

Note: This FGD guide should be used for discussions separately with groups of community health volunteers living in rural, urban, and refugee or IDP camp areas. The FGD participants are preferably direct beneficiaries of humanitarian interventions or at least living in communities benefitting from humanitarian interventions. All relevant questions in the KII have to be discussed, but this doesn't

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mean that they have to be all posed as such. Information should emerge from the discussion and through the tools. Additional questions might need to be posed to gather all relevant information.

Focus group discussions with Community health volunteers (CHVs or RECOs)

Quality Checklist³

Use the following checklist when conducting the Focus Group Discussions (FGDs).

		FGD
1	Do you have the recommended number of people in the FGD? (6-10 participants but can be fewer if not available at one place)	
2	Does the FGD include only participants that meet the pre-defined criteria?	
3	Have you selected a quiet and neutral place where no one else can hear what the participants say and where the participants feel comfortable?	
4	Have you selected a place that is safe, easy to reach, and accessible for all participants? (consider women, persons with disabilities, limited mobility, older persons, etc.)?	
5	Have you and the note taker introduced yourselves, and the Organization, and greeted the participants in a friendly manner?	
6	Have you asked the participants to introduce themselves?	
7	Have you explained the purpose of the FGD in a simple and easy-to-understand way?	
8	Have you assured the participants that their responses will be confidential and checked for everyone's consent to participate and/or for the discussion to be recorded?	
9	Have you explained to the participants that there are no consequences should they refuse to participate or should they decide to withdraw from the discussion at any point?	
10	Managing expectations: Have you explained to the participants that participation in the FGD will not automatically grant any benefits (current and future interventions)?	
11	Have you set the ground rules or asked the group to define their own rules?	

³ From PIN (2017) Quality Improvement & Verification Checklist For Focus Group Discussions, <https://resources.peopleinneed.net/files-search?q=focus#qualitative-data-collection-pin-2017-quality-improvement-verification-checklist-for-focus-group-discussions-154-98>

12	Gender and Inclusion: Have you ensured diversity in assessment activities and teams? <i>For example, ensure that the assessment team is gender balanced to facilitate contact and communication with women and girls; ensure that the language skills of the assessment team reflect languages used in the areas we are planning assessments.</i>		
13	Context-specific – Wherever possible and appropriate, have separate focus group discussion spaces been considered for specific groups (gender, age, ethnicity, disability, etc.) as necessary?		
14	Did you manage to ask all the questions in the FGD Guide?		
15	Have you thanked the participants for their time and participation?		
16	Did you make sure to ask the participants if they had any questions for us?		
Date:			
Location: <input type="checkbox"/> Rural <input type="checkbox"/> Urban <input type="checkbox"/> Camp			
Country: <input type="checkbox"/> DRC <input type="checkbox"/> South Sudan			
Region, village:			
Interviewer:			
Note taker(s):			
Participants (include the disaggregated figures)			
Number of Participants	Female	Male	Total
Persons with disability (physical)	Female	Male	Total
Persons with disability (intellectual)	Female	Male	Total
Elderly (60 and plus years)	Female	Male	Total

Key Area	Key question	Probes (what we need to understand)	Tool (how we can gather the information)
1. INFORMATION ON HUMANITARIAN ACTIVITY (15 min)	Which humanitarian organisations are active in your community and what do they do?	b. Which humanitarian organizations have been active in your community in the past two years? c. What types of interventions and projects have they carried out in your community in the past two years? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Has there been any support provided in terms of agriculture, food security, nutrition, shelter, WASH, health, or any other? ○ Have there been any distributions? What was distributed? ○ Have there been any rehabilitations and constructions? What has been rehabilitated/constructed? ○ Have there been any capacity-building activities? What topics were covered? Were any items distributed as a part of these capacity-building sessions? d. How many distributions took place in the last 2 years in your community? Do you know how many community members benefitted from different distributions?	A. HUMANITARIAN ACTIVITY MATRIX <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Use and fill in the Humanitarian Activity Matrix below (Qa, Qb). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draw a table and include in the first column the main sectors identified by participants (e.g. agriculture, nutrition, WASH, shelter etc.). • In the 2nd, 5th and 6th columns include the different activities of humanitarian organizations under each sector – a) distributions, b) rehabilitations, and c) capacity building. For each activity indicate who are the actors (NGOs) and provide details on the specific activities.
2. TYPES OF HUMANITARIAN WASTE (20 min)	What type of waste generated by humanitarian interventions can you see in your community?	24. What types of solid waste do you encounter in your community? Is any of it hazardous? Can you rank these types of waste from the most common to the least common? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Probe for plastic, paper, cardboard, glass, organic waste, hygienic waste (e.g. <i>diapers, pads</i>), textile, metal, construction waste, and hazardous waste. <i>Use the pictures of different types of waste.</i> 25. Where do these types of solid waste come from? (E.g. <i>market, agriculture, construction, NGO, etc.</i>) Are you able to recognize which type of waste is from activities of humanitarian organizations?	A. HUMANITARIAN ACTIVITY MATRIX <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Continue using and filling in the Humanitarian Activity Matrix below <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the 3rd column indicate which types of materials are most commonly distributed (Qc) and in the 4th column indicate how these materials are packaged (Qd). D. WASTE PICTURES / RANKING EXERCISE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Use pictures of different types of waste, including a) plastic, b) paper and cardboard, c) glass, d) organic waste, e) hygienic waste, f) textile, g) metal, h) construction waste, and i) hazardous waste. Bring blank papers to use in case the community identifies

		<p>26. What types of materials are most commonly distributed by NGOs in your community (e.g. <i>NFI kits, seeds, shelter kits...</i>)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If it is kits (WASH, shelter), probe for specific items in the kits. <p>27. How are these materials packaged when they are distributed? What different types of packaging materials do NGOs bring? (probe for different types of packaging)</p> <p>28. What humanitarian interventions bring the most waste into your community? (<i>Show pictures of different types of waste.</i>)</p> <p>29. What type of waste is most often brought into your community by humanitarian organizations? (<i>Show pictures of different types of waste.</i>)</p>	<p>another type of waste. Write this type on the paper and use it together with the other pictures.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First, ask the group to organize the pictures from the most common type of waste to the least common type of waste in their community (Qa). • Second, use it to help participants think about what humanitarian interventions bring the most waste (Qe). • Third, ask the group to organize the pictures from the most common type of waste to the least common type of waste brought by NGOs into their community (Qf).
<p>3. LOCATION OF WASTE AND HUMANITARIAN WASTE <i>(25 min)</i></p>	<p>Where can we usually find solid waste in your community and where is the waste from humanitarian interventions usually located?</p>	<p>34. Where do distributions usually take place? Can you please show me the location after our discussion? (<i>use Kobo</i>)</p> <p>35. Do you/distribution recipients usually unpack the distributed materials at the site of the distribution, on the road, at home or somewhere else?</p> <p>36. When was the last distribution?</p> <p>37. Can some of you after our group discussion practically show me what you or your community do with</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ the distributed items once they cannot be used anymore and where they are now? ○ the packaging from the last distribution and where it is now? ○ the construction waste from rehabilitations (if any)? (<i>use Kobo</i>) <p>38. Does most of the distribution of a) items, b) packaging, and c) construction waste end up in the community, outside of the community, designated community dump, or is it being collected by a waste management service or transported to a waste recycling company?</p>	<p>E. KOBO OBSERVATION TOOL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Use the Kobo Observation tool to observe the state/quality of waste, take photos of the distribution and rehabilitation sites as well as any dump sites, and GPS location after the FGD finishes (Qa, Qd, Qf).

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Is it any different from other non-humanitarian waste? <p>39. Can some of you after our group discussion show me the location(s) where most of the waste is now, including any official and unofficial dump sites? (<i>use Kobo</i>)</p>	
<p>4. QUANTITY, QUALITY AND APPEARANCE OF WASTE AND HUMANITARIAN WASTE</p> <p><i>(20 min)</i></p>	<p>When does waste usually appear in your community and how is it protected? What is the quantity and quality of waste generated in your community and of waste brought by NGOs?</p>	<p>15. Does <u>waste in general</u> appear in your community/dump sites continually or are there periods when there is more waste and less waste? If yes, when and why?</p> <p>16. Does <u>humanitarian waste</u> appear in your community/dump sites continually or are there periods when there is more waste and less waste? If yes, when and why?</p> <p>17. Do you know someone who knows or can estimate the amount of waste produced in your community?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If there is no such person, why? <p>18. Does your community/municipality have any institutions that take measures to protect your waste from destruction (e.g. weather) or being taken by someone or is the waste left without any supervision and protection?</p> <p>19. Is there any waste that harms the environment (air, soil, water) or causes health problems to people? How?</p>	
<p>5. WASTE IN HEALTH FACILITIES</p> <p><i>(15 min)</i></p>	<p>What are the types of waste produced by HFs and obtained by HFs from NGOs?</p>	<p>11. What types of solid waste does your health facility produce? What hazardous solid waste is produced there?</p> <p>12. What type of materials does your HF receive from NGOs during distributions (e.g. Plumpynut, F75, F100, medication, sanitation materials, WASH materials)? What type of rehabilitation (if any) were received?</p> <p>13. In the past 2 years, have there been other materials distributed to the community through your HF? If yes, which ones?</p>	<p>A. HUMANITARIAN ACTIVITY MATRIX</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ You can use the Humanitarian Activity Matrix below to record some of the answers in this section (Qb, Qc, Qd). <p>E. KOBO OBSERVATION TOOL</p> <p>Use the Kobo Observation tool to observe materials distributed by NGOs that are in the health facility, take photos, and GPS location after the FGD finishes (Qd).</p>

		<p>14. What is the packaging material usually used by NGOs during distributions in/to your HF? Can you show me?</p> <p>15. Do the distributed items and packaging materials from distributions done in your HF usually stay in the HF? Does the packaging material from distributions to the community done through your HF usually stay at the HF premises or is it taken home by the beneficiaries?</p>	
<p>6. HOUSEHOLD WASTE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES</p> <p><i>(30 min)</i></p>	<p>What do households do with their solid waste and who decides? Are the current practices different from the past?</p>	<p>16. Who in your <u>household</u> usually decides what to do with a) used distribution items, b) packaging from distributions, and c) other waste?</p> <p>17. Who in your <u>community</u> usually decides what to do with a) used distribution items, b) packaging from distributions, and c) other waste?</p> <p>18. What do households in your community do with a) used distribution items, b) packaging from distributions, and c) other waste? Do your community households re-use it, recycle it, compost it, throw it away, or burn it?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If your community re-uses it, how, and for what? Can you show me after the discussion? ○ If your community recycles it, where, and how? Can you show me after the discussion? ○ If your community composts it, where, and how? Can you show me after the discussion? ○ If your community throws it away, where? Can you show me after the discussion? ○ If your community burns it, where, and how often? Which type of packaging do you/your community burn? <p>19. Do your current practices of handling solid waste differ from your tradition in the past? If yes, what are the differences?</p> <p>20. Is there any <u>solid waste</u> that your community <u>likes</u> to have? Why?</p>	<p>B. HOUSEHOLD WASTE MANAGEMENT MATRIX</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Use and fill in the Household Waste Management Matrix below. Use the waste pictures from the ranking exercise. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First, ask the group how the households in their community manage their waste (re-use, recycle, compost, throw away, burn). Afterward, ask clarifying questions: How? For what? Where? How often? <p>E. KOBO OBSERVATION TOOL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Use the Kobo Observation tool to observe how the community re-uses, recycles and composts solid waste, and take photos of the process and GPS location after the FGD finishes (Qc).

		<p>21. Is there any <u>solid waste</u> that your community <u>doesn't like</u> to have? Why?</p> <p>22. Are there any distribution items and packaging that you find useful for other purposes?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Which materials are useful for which purposes? How long can you reuse it? What do you do when it is not useful anymore? <p>23. Are there any distribution items and packaging that you do not like to receive during distributions? Why?</p>	
<p>7. WASTE MANAGEMENT INSTITUTIONS IN COMMUNITIES <i>(30 min)</i></p>	<p>What are the waste management institutions and individuals active in communities, how do they function and what are their responsibilities?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Are there any community rules for solid waste management? What are they? 2. Are there any community institutions/offices/NGOs/individuals (e.g. <i>informal waste pickers</i>) that are responsible for solid waste collection and management in your community? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What are they? What are their responsibilities? Which waste do they manage? How do they function? 3. Does your community have an official or unofficial dump site? Do you/your community use it? Can I see it after the discussion? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Who manages it? Who manages the transportation of waste to the dump site? If there is a fee for waste collection, how much does it cost and who pays it? How do they keep records of who paid? ○ How does it look like? Is it an unprotected open space or is the waste storage space hardened, fenced, and illuminated? Is there water, sewage system, electricity, and emission and pollution monitoring systems available? 4. Are there any waste recycling or composting businesses in or near your community? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If yes, what businesses are these and what types of solid waste do they recycle or compost? 	<p>C. WASTE MANAGEMENT INSTITUTIONS MATRIX</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Use and fill in the Institutions Waste Management Institutions Matrix below. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First, ask the group if there are any community institutions/offices/NGOs/individuals responsible for solid waste collection and management. Afterwards, ask about their responsibilities, which type of waste, and from where they manage, and how they function (Qb, Qc, Qd, Qe). <p>E. KOBO OBSERVATION TOOL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Use the Kobo Observation tool to observe the community official or unofficial dump site, take photos, and GPS location after the FGD finishes (Qc).

		<p>5. Are there any informal recyclers or re-users in your community?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Who are they and how many? How do they work? Where, how often, and what type of waste do they collect? ○ What do they do with the waste? Do they re-use or recycle it by themselves or do they hand it over to a third party? Which one? What happens next? ○ What is the general perception of these informal recyclers? <p>6. Is it possible for your community to limit the amount of solid waste it produces? If yes, what would be the possible solutions?</p> <p>7. What is the biggest challenge in terms of solid waste management for you (<i>e.g inability to pay fees, community behavior</i>)? If possible, distinguish between waste from NGOs and other waste.</p>	
<p>8. WASTE IN HEALTH FACILITIES</p> <p><i>(30 min)</i></p>	<p>How is solid waste managed in your health facilities, what are the main practices and who are the key actors?</p>	<p>13. What does your health facility and community do with a) the waste produced by the health facility and b) obtained from NGOs (including distributions and rehabilitations)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Are there any specific solid waste management standards that are applied to the health facility? What are they? ○ Does the HF have an incinerator? Which type of SW is incinerated? How often? ○ Which type of solid waste is burned? Where? How often? ○ Which type of solid waste is thrown away? Where? ○ Are there placenta tips or any other type of traditional waste disposal practices? ○ Are there informal community solid waste recyclers/re-users that handpick/collect the HF waste and reuse/recycle/resell the waste? If yes, who are these recyclers/re-users and what 	<p>C. WASTE MANAGEMENT INSTITUTIONS MATRIX</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Some of this information can be collected through the Institutions Waste Management Institutions Matrix below. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First, ask the group if there are any community institutions/offices/NGOs/individuals responsible for solid waste collection and management. Afterwards, ask about their responsibilities, which type of waste, and from where they manage, and how they function (Qa, Qb, Qc). If possible, distinguish between humanitarian and other waste. <p>E. KOBO OBSERVATION TOOL</p> <p>Use the Kobo Observation tool to observe health facility waste management, take photos, and GPS location after the FGD finishes (Qa).</p>

		<p>type of waste and how often do they pick/collect?</p> <p>14. Is there a community waste management service that collects the waste the HF produces? What is the name of this service? How often does it collect the waste? Does it collect all types of waste (incl. hazardous waste) or only a specific type?</p> <p>15. Is any type of solid waste handed over to an official recycling business?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o If yes, which type of solid waste is handed to this business? What is the name of this business? Are there any fees applied? Who is responsible for the transport of the waste? <p>16. Is your current way of handling the solid waste you produce and receive from NGOs different from the traditional practices in the past? If yes, how?</p> <p>17. Is it possible that your HF limits the solid waste that you produce? What would be the solutions?</p>	
<p>9. HUMANITARIAN WASTE SOLUTIONS</p> <p>(30 min)</p>	<p>What are the challenges and opportunities of humanitarian waste management in your community?</p>	<p>44. What is the biggest challenge in terms of solid waste management for you (<i>e.g. inability to pay fees, community behavior</i>)? If possible, distinguish between waste from NGOs and other waste.</p> <p>45. How can the current way of handling a) used items distributed by NGOs (when these items become waste after being used), b) packaging from items distributed by NGOs, and c) other waste (<i>e.g. construction</i>) from NGOs be improved within a) your community and b) your health facility?</p> <p>46. What would you need to improve the current handling of a) used items, b) packaging, and c) other waste (<i>e.g. from construction</i>) from NGOs in a) your community and b) your health facility?</p> <p>47. Are there any local actors/institutions/businesses that could contribute and provide solutions?</p> <p>48. Are there any opportunities for improving solid waste management that NGOs are not making use of?</p>	

		8. Do you know of any examples of reusing or recycling of solid waste generated by NGOs practiced in your community?	
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A. Humanitarian Activity Matrix

Note: Start by asking in which humanitarian organizations are active in the community and what types of interventions and projects they have carried out in the community in the past two years. Add additional rows if needed.

Type of humanitarian support:	If there were any <u>distributions</u> in this sector, specify (E.g. seeds; WASH kits; ready-to-use therapeutic food, etc.). Note the name of the humanitarian organization.	Indicate how common this type of distribution is (very common, medium common, little common).	Indicate all the types of packaging the specific distributed items are wrapped in.	If there were any <u>rehabilitation or constructions</u> in this sector, specify (E.g. latrine construction, school rehabilitation, etc.). Note the name of the humanitarian organization.	If there were any <u>capacity-building sessions</u> in this sector, specify (E.g. IYCF and cooking sessions, agriculture-related training, GBV training, etc.). Note the name of the humanitarian organization.
Agriculture and food security					
Nutrition					
Health					
WASH					
Shelter					

B. Household Waste Management Matrix

Note: Start by asking what households in the community do with different types of waste; whether they re-use, recycle, compost, burn or throw it away. Afterward, ask clarifying questions: How? For what? Where? How often? **Specify if the waste is a) used items from distributions, b) packaging from distributions, and c) other waste.**

	Re-use - How? For what?	Recycle - Where? How?	Compost - Where? How?	Burn - Where? How often?	Throw away - Where?
Plastic waste					
Paper and cardboard					
Glass					
Organic waste					
Hygienic waste					
Textile					
Metal waste					
Construction waste					

Hazardous waste					
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C. Waste Management Institutions Matrix

Note: Start by asking if there are any community institutions/offices/NGOs/individuals responsible for solid waste collection and management. Afterward, ask about their responsibilities, which type of waste they manage, and how they function.

Institution type (e.g. NGO, government, business, individual – e.g. informal recyclers)	Institution name	What type of waste they manage and from where (e.g. from health facilities, households, etc.) (use the photos of different types of waste)	Responsibilities (e.g. if they collect waste, sort & grade waste, recycle waste, re-use waste, compost, manage dump site, etc.)	How they function (e.g. if they collect fees, how often they do specific activities, if they hand over waste to someone else etc.)

D3.3 – Annex 10

BIO4HUMAN FGD Guide for Humanitarian SWM Needs Assessment (WP3, T3.3)

Scope: The assessment has the aim of gathering information on the types of waste in DRC and South Sudan, traditional and current methods of SWM, identification of humanitarian supply chains and leaders, and identification of needs of the humanitarian sector in SWM.

Note: This FGD guide should be used for discussions separately with groups of women and groups of men, as well as for groups of persons living in rural, urban, and refugee or IDP camp areas. The FGD participants are preferably direct beneficiaries of humanitarian interventions or at least living in communities benefitting from humanitarian interventions. All relevant questions in the FGD have to be discussed but this doesn't mean that they have to be all posed as such. Information should emerge from the discussion and through the tools. Additional questions might need to be posed to gather all relevant information.

Focus group discussions with the Community

Quality Checklist⁴

Use the following checklist when conducting the Focus Group Discussions (FGDs).

		FGD
1	Do you have the recommended number of people in the FGD? (6-10 participants)	
2	Does the FGD include only participants that meet the pre-defined criteria?	

⁴ From PIN (2017) Quality Improvement & Verification Checklist For Focus Group Discussions, <https://resources.peopleinneed.net/files-search?q=focus#qualitative-data-collection-pin-2017-quality-improvement-verification-checklist-for-focus-group-discussions-154-98>

3	Have you selected a quiet and neutral place where no one else can hear what the participants say and where the participants feel comfortable?	
4	Have you selected a place that is safe, easy to reach, and accessible for all participants? (consider women, persons with disabilities, limited mobility, older persons, etc.)?	
5	Have you and the note taker introduced yourselves, and the Organization, and greeted the participants in a friendly manner?	
6	Have you asked the participants to introduce themselves?	
7	Have you explained the purpose of the FGD in a simple and easy-to-understand way?	
8	Have you assured the participants that their responses will be confidential and checked for everyone's consent to participate and/or for the discussion to be recorded?	
9	Have you explained to the participants that there are no consequences should they refuse to participate or should they decide to withdraw from the discussion at any point?	
10	Managing expectations: Have you explained to the participants that participation in the FGD will not automatically grant any benefits (current and future interventions)?	
11	Have you set the ground rules or asked the group to define their own rules?	
12	Gender and Inclusion: Have you ensured diversity in assessment activities and teams? <i>For example, ensure that the assessment team is gender balanced to facilitate contact and communication with women and girls; ensure that the language skills of the assessment team reflect languages used in the areas we are planning assessments.</i>	
13	Context-specific – Wherever possible and appropriate, have separate focus group discussion spaces been considered for specific groups (gender, age, ethnicity, disability, etc.) as necessary?	
14	Did you manage to ask all the questions in the FGD Guide?	
15	Have you thanked the participants for their time and participation?	
16	Did you make sure to ask the participants if they had any questions for us?	
Date:		

Location: <input type="checkbox"/> Rural <input type="checkbox"/> Urban <input type="checkbox"/> Camp		Country: <input type="checkbox"/> DRC <input type="checkbox"/> South Sudan		Region, village:	
Interviewer:					
Note taker(s):					
Participants (include the disaggregated figures)					
Number of Participants	Female		Male		Total
Persons with disability (physical)	Female		Male		Total
Persons with disability (intellectual)	Female		Male		Total
Elderly (60 and plus years)	Female		Male		Total

Key Area	Key question	Probes (what we need to understand)	Tool (how we can gather the information)
1. INFORMATION ON HUMANITARIAN ACTIVITY (15 min)	Which humanitarian organisations are active in your community and what do they do?	e. Which humanitarian organizations have been active in your community in the past two years? f. What types of interventions and projects have they carried out in your community in the past two years? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Has there been any support provided in terms of agriculture, food security, nutrition, shelter, WASH, health, or any other? ○ Have there been any distributions? What was distributed? ○ Have there been any rehabilitations and constructions? What has been rehabilitated/constructed? ○ Have there been any capacity-building activities? What topics were covered? Were any items distributed as a part of these capacity-building sessions? g. How many distributions took place in the last 2 years in your community? Do you know how many community members benefitted from different distributions?	A. HUMANITARIAN ACTIVITY MATRIX <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Use and fill in the Humanitarian Activity Matrix below (Qa, Qb). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draw a table and include in the first column the main sectors identified by participants (e.g. agriculture, nutrition, WASH, shelter, etc.). • In the 2nd, 5th and 6th columns include the different activities of humanitarian organizations under each sector – a) distributions, b) rehabilitations, and c) capacity building. For each activity indicate who are the actors (NGOs) and provide details on the specific activities.
2. TYPES OF HUMANITARIAN WASTE (30 min)	What type of waste generated by humanitarian interventions can you see in your community?	30. What types of solid waste do you encounter in your community? Is any of it hazardous? Can you rank these types of waste from the most common to the least common? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Probe for plastic, paper, cardboard, glass, organic waste, hygienic waste (e.g. <i>diapers, pads</i>), textile, metal, construction waste, and hazardous waste. <i>Use the pictures of different types of waste.</i> 31. Where do these types of solid waste come from? (E.g. <i>market, agriculture, construction, NGO, etc.</i>) Are you able to recognize which	A. HUMANITARIAN ACTIVITY MATRIX <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Continue using and filling in the Humanitarian Activity Matrix below <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the 3rd column indicate which types of materials are most commonly distributed (Qc) and in the 4th column indicate how these materials are packaged (Qd). D. WASTE PICTURES / RANKING EXERCISE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Use pictures of different types of waste, including a) plastic, b) paper and cardboard, c) glass, d) organic waste, e) hygienic waste, f)

		<p>type of waste is from activities of humanitarian organizations?</p> <p>32. What types of materials are most commonly distributed by NGOs in your community (e.g. <i>NFI kits, seeds, shelter kits...</i>)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If it is kits (WASH, shelter), probe for specific items in the kits. <p>33. How are these materials packaged when they are distributed? What different types of packaging materials do NGOs bring? (probe for different types of packaging)</p> <p>34. What humanitarian interventions bring the most waste into your community? (<i>Show pictures of different types of waste.</i>)</p> <p>35. What type of waste is most often brought into your community by humanitarian organizations? (<i>Show pictures of different types of waste.</i>)</p>	<p>textile, g) metal, h) construction waste, and i) hazardous waste. Bring blank papers to use in case the community identifies another type of waste. Write this type on the paper and use it together with the other pictures.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First, ask the group to organize the pictures from the most common type of waste to the least common type of waste in their community (Qa). • Second, use it to help participants think about what humanitarian interventions bring the most waste (Qe). • Third, ask the group to organize the pictures from the most common type of waste to the least common type of waste brought by NGOs into their community (Qf).
<p>3. LOCATION OF WASTE AND HUMANITARIAN WASTE (25 min)</p>	<p>Where can we usually find solid waste in your community and where is the waste from humanitarian interventions usually located?</p>	<p>40. Where do distributions usually take place? Can you please show me the location after our discussion? (<i>use Kobo</i>)</p> <p>41. Do you/distribution recipients usually unpack the distributed materials at the site of the distribution, on the road, at home, or somewhere else?</p> <p>42. When was the last distribution?</p> <p>43. Can some of you after our group discussion practically show me what you or your community do with</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ the distributed items once they cannot be used anymore and where they are now? ○ the packaging from the last distribution and where it is now? ○ the construction waste from rehabilitations (if any)? (<i>use Kobo</i>) <p>44. Does most of the distribution of a) items, b) packaging, and c) construction waste end up in</p>	<p>E. KOBO OBSERVATION TOOL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Use the Kobo Observation tool to observe the state/quality of waste, take photos of the distribution and rehabilitation sites as well as any dump sites, and GPS location after the FGD finishes (Qa, Qd, Qf).

		<p>the community, outside of the community, designated community dump, or is it being collected by a waste management service or transported to a waste recycling company?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Is it any different from other non-humanitarian waste? <p>45. Can some of you after our group discussion show me the location(s) where most of the waste is now, including any official and unofficial dump sites? <i>(use Kobo)</i></p>	
<p>4. QUANTITY, QUALITY AND APPEARANCE OF WASTE AND HUMANITARIAN WASTE</p> <p><i>(20 min)</i></p>	<p>When does waste usually appear in your community and how is it protected? What is the quantity and quality of waste generated in your community and of waste brought by NGOs?</p>	<p>20. Does <u>waste in general</u> appear in your community/dump sites continually or are there periods when there is more waste and less waste? If yes, when and why?</p> <p>21. Does <u>humanitarian waste</u> appear in your community/dump sites continually or are there periods when there is more waste and less waste? If yes, when and why?</p> <p>22. Do you know someone who knows or can estimate the amount of waste produced in your community?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If there is no such person, why? <p>23. Does your community/municipality have any institutions that take measures to protect your waste from destruction (e.g. weather) or being taken by someone or is the waste left without any supervision and protection?</p> <p>24. Is there any waste that harms the environment (air, soil, water) or causes health problems to people? How?</p>	
<p>5. HOUSEHOLD WASTE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES</p> <p><i>(30 min)</i></p>	<p>What do households do with their solid waste and who decides? Are the current practices different from the past?</p>	<p>24. Who in your <u>household</u> usually decides what to do with a) used distribution items, b) packaging from distributions, and c) other waste?</p> <p>25. Who in your <u>community</u> usually decides what to do with a) used distribution items, b)</p>	<p>B. HOUSEHOLD WASTE MANAGEMENT MATRIX</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Use and fill in the Household Waste Management Matrix below. Use the waste pictures from the ranking exercise. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First, ask the group how the households in their community manage their waste (re-use, recycle, compost, throw away, burn).

		<p>packaging from distributions, and c) other waste?</p> <p>26. What do households in your community do with a) used distribution items, b) packaging from distributions, and c) other waste? Do your community households re-use it, recycle it, compost it, throw away or burn it?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If your community re-uses it, how and for what? Can you show me after the discussion? ○ If your community recycles it, where and how? Can you show me after the discussion? ○ If your community composts it, where and how? Can you show me after the discussion? ○ If your community throws it away, where? Can you show me after the discussion? ○ If your community burns it, where and how often? Which type of packaging do you/your community burn? <p>27. Do your current practices of handling solid waste differ from your tradition in the past? If yes, what are the differences?</p> <p>28. Is there any <u>solid waste</u> that your community <u>likes</u> to have? Why?</p> <p>29. Is there any <u>solid waste</u> that your community <u>doesn't like</u> to have? Why?</p> <p>30. Are there any distribution items and packaging that you find useful for other purposes?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Which materials are useful for which purposes? How long can you reuse it? What do you do when it is not useful anymore? <p>31. Are there any distribution items and packaging that you do not like to receive during distributions? Why?</p>	<p>Afterward, ask clarifying questions: How? For what? Where? How often?</p> <p>E. KOBO OBSERVATION TOOL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Use the Kobo Observation tool to observe how the community re-uses, recycle and compost solid waste, take photos of the process and GPS location after the FGD finishes (Qc).
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<p>6. WASTE MANAGEMENT INSTITUTIONS IN COMMUNITIES</p> <p>(30 min)</p>	<p>What are the waste management institutions and individuals active in communities, how do they function and what are their responsibilities?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Are there any community rules for solid waste management? What are they? 2. Are there any community institutions/offices/NGOs/individuals (e.g. <i>informal waste pickers</i>) that are responsible for solid waste collection and management in your community? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What are they? What are their responsibilities? Which waste do they manage? How do they function? 3. Does your community have an official or unofficial dump site? Do you/your community use it? Can I see it after the discussion? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Who manages it? Who manages the transportation of waste to the dump site? If there is a fee for waste collection, how much does it cost and who pays it? How do they keep records of who paid? ○ How does it look like? Is it an unprotected open space or is the waste storage space hardened, fenced and illuminated? Is there water, sewage system, electricity, and emission and pollution monitoring systems available? 4. Are there any waste recycling or composting businesses in or nearby your community? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If yes, what businesses are these and what types of solid waste do they recycle or compost? ○ Does your community hand over your waste to this business for recycling or composting? How often and which type of solid waste? Does the business have the capacity to recycle/compost all the solid waste of the given type that your community produces? Are there any fees applied? 	<p>C. WASTE MANAGEMENT INSTITUTIONS MATRIX</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Use and fill in the Institutions Waste Management Institutions Matrix below. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First, ask the group if there are any community institutions/offices/NGOs/individuals responsible for solid waste collection and management. Afterward, ask about their responsibilities, which type of waste they manage, and how they function (Qb, Qc, Qd, Qe). <p>E. KOBO OBSERVATION TOOL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Use the Kobo Observation tool to observe the community official or unofficial dump site, take photos, and GPS location after the FGD finishes (Qc).
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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If your community does not use the recycling and/or composting service, why? ○ If your community hands over your waste to a recycling or composting business, how do you ensure the protection of waste from destruction (rotting, severe weather conditions) and from being taken by others? <p>5. Are there any informal recyclers or re-users in your community?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Who are they and how many? How do they work? Where, how often, and what type of waste do they collect? ○ What do they do with the waste? Do they re-use or recycle it by themselves or do they hand it over to a third party? Which one? What happens next? ○ What is the general perception of these informal recyclers? <p>6. Is it possible for your community to limit the amount of solid waste it produces? If yes, what would be the possible solutions?</p> <p>7. What is the biggest challenge in terms of solid waste management for you (e.g. <i>inability to pay fees, community behavior</i>)? If possible, distinguish between waste from NGOs and other waste.</p>	
7. HUMANITARIAN WASTE SOLUTIONS (30 min)	What are the challenges and opportunities of humanitarian waste management in your community?	<p>a. What is the biggest challenge in terms of solid waste management for you (e.g. <i>inability to pay fees, community behaviour</i>)? If possible, distinguish between waste from NGOs and other waste.</p> <p>b. How can the current way of handling packaging and other waste from NGOs be improved?</p>	

- | | | | |
|--|--|---|--|
| | | <ul style="list-style-type: none">c. What would you need to improve the current handling of packaging and other waste from NGOs?d. Are there any local actors/institutions/businesses that could contribute and provide solutions?e. Are there any opportunities for improving solid waste management that NGOs are not making use of?a. Do you know of any examples of reusing or recycling of solid waste generated by NGOs practiced in your community? | |
|--|--|---|--|

A. Humanitarian Activity Matrix

Note: Start by asking in which humanitarian organizations are active in the community and what types of interventions and projects they have carried out in the community in the past two years. Add additional rows if needed.

Type of humanitarian support:	If there were any <u>distributions</u> in this sector, specify (E.g. seeds; WASH kits; ready-to-use therapeutic food etc.). Note the name of the humanitarian organization.	Indicate how common this type of distribution is (very common, medium common, little common).	Indicate all the types of packaging the specific distributed items are wrapped in.	If there were any <u>rehabilitation or constructions</u> in this sector, specify (E.g. latrine construction, school rehabilitation etc.). Note the name of the humanitarian organization.	If there were any <u>capacity-building sessions</u> in this sector, specify (E.g. IYCF and cooking sessions, agriculture-related training, GBV training etc.). Note the name of the humanitarian organization.
Agriculture and food security					
Nutrition					
Health					
WASH					
Shelter					

B. Household Waste Management Matrix

Note: Start by asking what households in the community do with different types of waste; whether they re-use, recycle, compost, burn or throw it away. Afterward, ask clarifying questions: How? For what? Where? How often? **Specify if the waste is a) used items from distributions, b) packaging from distributions, c) and other waste.**

	Re-use - How? For what?	Recycle - Where? How?	Compost - Where? How?	Burn - Where? How often?	Throw away - Where?
Plastic waste					
Paper and cardboard					
Glass					
Organic waste					
Hygienic waste					
Textile					
Metal waste					
Construction waste					

Hazardous waste					
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C. Waste Management Institutions Matrix

Note: Start by asking if there are any community institutions/offices/NGOs/individuals responsible for solid waste collection and management. Afterward, ask about their responsibilities, which type of waste they manage, and how they function.

a. Institution type (e.g. NGO, government, business, individual – e.g. informal recyclers)	Institution name	What type of waste they manage (use the photos of different types of waste)	Responsibilities (e.g. if they collect waste, sort & grade waste, recycle waste, re-use waste, compost, manage dump site etc.)	How they function (e.g. if they collect fees, how often they do specific activities, if they hand over waste to someone else etc.)
